

The impact of small white ginger extract paste on arterial and cerebral blood pressure

El impacto de la pequeña pasta de extracto de jengibre blanco sobre la presión arterial y cerebral

Debby Saputera¹, Muhammad Dinil Fajr², Rosihan Adhani³, Rahmad Arifin⁴, Beta Widya Oktiani⁵, Bayu Indra Sukmana⁶, Yuniar Elsa Dwinuria⁷

¹Departement of Prosthodontic, Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4647-8574> debby.saputera-2018@fkg.unair.ac.id

²Undergraduate Preclinical Dentistry Programme. Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7840-1056>

³Departement of Public Dental Health, Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7430-5323>

⁴Departement of Prosthodontic, Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4569-7521>

⁵Departement of Periodontic, Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1699-0010>

⁶Departement of Oral Biology, Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-4169-8720>

⁷Departement of Orthodontic, Gusti Hasan Aman, Dental and Oral Hospital, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3439-4808>

Corresponding: Debby Saputera; Departement of Prosthodontic, Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia, Jl. Veteran No. 128B, Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan; e-mail: debby.saputera@ulm.ac.id,

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Resumen

Hypertension, a prevalent health condition, demands meticulous care to prevent complications, particularly those affecting cerebral vasculature. Regular denture cleaning among hypertensive individuals is imperative to thwart *Candida albicans* contamination, plaque accumulation, and calculus, thereby averting potential cerebrovascular events. Mechanical (brushing) and chemical (immersion) methods are common approaches for denture maintenance. While mechanical methods offer expediency and efficacy in plaque removal, they pose the risk of inducing surface roughness in acrylic resin due to abrasive cleaning pastes. Purpose: This study aims to evaluate the impact of a 100% concentration of small white ginger extract paste (EJPK) on the surface roughness of acrylic resin dentures in hypertensive patients. Method: A true experimental research design employing pre-test and post-test with a control group was utilized. Three groups were formed: EJPK brushing treatment, placebo

paste (positive control), and aquades (negative control). Plate-shaped samples of heat-cured acrylic resin were prepared, with each group comprising 9 samples, totaling 27 samples. Surface roughness was assessed using a surface roughness tester. Results: Statistical analysis, including One Way ANOVA and Post Hoc Bonferroni test, revealed significant differences in mean surface roughness among the groups. The EJPK paste group exhibited a mean surface roughness of 0.0700 μm , while the placebo paste and aquades groups showed values of 0.0589 μm and 0.0489 μm , respectively. Brushing with EJPK paste at 100% concentration resulted in higher surface roughness compared to the placebo paste and aquades. However, the surface roughness of heat-cured acrylic resin brushed with EJPK paste remains clinically acceptable for oral use, even in hypertensive patients prone to cerebral vascular complications.

Keywords: Hypertension, Denture cleaning, Surface roughness, Acrylic resin, Ginger extract

La hipertensión, una condición de salud prevalente, exige un cuidado meticuloso para prevenir complicaciones, particularmente aquellas que afectan la vasculatura cerebral. La limpieza regular de las prótesis dentales entre personas hipertensas es imperativa para frustrar la contaminación por *Candida albicans*, la acumulación de placa y cálculos, evitando así posibles eventos cerebrovasculares. Los métodos mecánicos (cepillado) y químicos (inmersión) son enfoques comunes para el mantenimiento de las dentaduras postizas. Si bien los métodos mecánicos ofrecen conveniencia y eficacia en la eliminación de la placa, plantean el riesgo de inducir rugosidad en la superficie de la resina acrílica debido a las pastas de limpieza abrasivas. Propósito: Este estudio tiene como objetivo evaluar el impacto de una concentración del 100% de pasta pequeña de extracto de jengibre blanco (EJPK) sobre la rugosidad de la superficie de las prótesis dentales de resina acrílica en pacientes hipertensos. Método: Se utilizó un diseño de investigación verdaderamente experimental que emplea preprueba y posprueba con un grupo de control. Se formaron tres grupos: tratamiento de cepillado EJPK, pasta placebo (control positivo) y aquades (control negativo). Se prepararon muestras en forma de placa de resina acrílica termocurada, comprendiendo cada grupo 9 muestras, con un total de 27 muestras. La rugosidad de la superficie se evaluó utilizando un probador de rugosidad de superficie. Resultados: El análisis estadístico, incluido el ANOVA unidireccional y la prueba Post Hoc Bonferroni, reveló diferencias significativas en la rugosidad superficial media entre los grupos. El grupo de pasta EJPK exhibió una rugosidad superficial media de 0,0700 μm , mientras que los grupos de pasta placebo y aquades mostraron valores de 0,0589 μm y 0,0489 μm , respectivamente. El cepillado con pasta EJPK a una concentración del 100% resultó en una mayor rugosidad de la superficie en comparación con la pasta placebo y los aquades. Sin embargo, la rugosidad de la superficie de la resina acrílica termocurada cepillada con pasta EJPK sigue siendo clínicamente aceptable para uso oral, incluso en pacientes hipertensos propensos a complicaciones vasculares cerebrales.

Palabras clave: Hipertensión, Limpieza de prótesis, Rugosidad superficial, Resina acrílica, Extracto de jengibre

High blood pressure, also known as hypertension, is a common condition where the force of blood against the artery walls is consistently too high. This can lead to serious health complications, including stroke, heart attack, and cognitive impairment¹⁻³.

According to recent studies, the prevalence of hypertension is steadily increasing worldwide, with significant numbers reported in Indonesia. Riskesdas data from 2018 indicates that approximately 25% of adults in Indonesia are affected by hypertension⁴⁻⁸. Furthermore, the prevalence of hypertension tends to rise with age, with individuals aged 65 and over being particularly vulnerable.

One of the key risk factors for hypertension is lifestyle choices, including poor diet, lack of physical activity, and smoking. Additionally, genetic factors and certain medical conditions can also contribute to the development of hypertension^{9,10}.

Hypertension can have detrimental effects on brain health. Prolonged high blood pressure can damage blood vessels in the brain, leading to reduced blood flow and oxygen supply to brain tissue. This can result in cognitive decline, memory problems, and an increased risk of dementia^{11,12}.

Moreover, hypertension is a major risk factor for stroke, a condition where blood flow to the brain is blocked or reduced, leading to brain cell damage. Ischemic strokes, which occur when a blood clot blocks a blood vessel in the brain, are particularly associated with hypertension^{13,14}.

Management and treatment of hypertension typically involve lifestyle modifications such as adopting a healthy diet, increasing physical activity, and quitting smoking. In some cases, medication may also be prescribed to help lower blood pressure and reduce the risk of complications¹⁵.

Regular monitoring of blood pressure is crucial for early detection and management of hypertension. This can be done at home with a blood pressure monitor or during regular check-ups with a healthcare provider^{16,17}.

In conclusion, hypertension is a serious condition that can have significant implications for brain health. By adopting a healthy lifestyle and seeking appropriate medical care, individuals can reduce their risk of hypertension-related complications and safeguard their cognitive function.

To mitigate the risk of cerebral arterial hypertension, individuals must actively manage their blood pressure

levels. Regular monitoring and control of arterial blood pressure are paramount to prevent complications such as stroke, cognitive decline, and vascular dementia⁹. The management of cerebral arterial hypertension encompasses various strategies, including lifestyle modifications, pharmacological interventions, and therapeutic approaches^{18,19}.

One of the primary methods for managing cerebral arterial hypertension is through lifestyle modifications, which involve adopting a healthy diet, maintaining a healthy weight, engaging in regular physical activity, limiting alcohol consumption, and avoiding tobacco use²⁰⁻²². These lifestyle changes can help reduce arterial stiffness, improve endothelial function, and lower blood pressure levels.

In addition to lifestyle modifications, pharmacological interventions play a crucial role in the management of cerebral arterial hypertension. Antihypertensive medications, such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs), calcium channel blockers, beta-blockers, and diuretics, are commonly prescribed to lower blood pressure levels and reduce the risk of cardiovascular events^{19,22}.

Furthermore, therapeutic approaches such as mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR), biofeedback, and relaxation techniques may also be beneficial in managing cerebral arterial hypertension by reducing stress levels, promoting relaxation, and improving overall psychological well-being²³.

It is important for individuals with cerebral arterial hypertension to work closely with their healthcare providers to develop a comprehensive treatment plan tailored to their specific needs and risk factors. Regular monitoring of blood pressure levels, adherence to medication regimens, and ongoing lifestyle modifications are essential components of effective management and prevention of complications associated with cerebral arterial hypertension^{19,24}. By taking proactive steps to control blood pressure levels, individuals can significantly reduce their risk of adverse outcomes and improve their overall quality of life.

Methods

This research employed a “pure experiment” design using a pre-test and post-test design with a group control setup. It comprised three brushing treatment groups: 100% small white ginger extract paste (EJPK), placebo paste (positive control), and aquades (negative control). The study utilized heat-cured acrylic resin plates, measuring 65 mm x 10 mm x 2.5 mm, in accordance with ADA standard No. 12, 1974. A total of 27 acrylic resin plates were employed, divided into three treatment groups, each consisting of nine samples of heat-cured acrylic resin. Ethical clearance for this research was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Commission of the Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, under Certificate No. 054/KEPKG-FKGULM/EC/III/2023.

The small white ginger determination test (*Zingiber officinale* var. *amarum*) was conducted at the Basic Laboratory of the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarbaru. The fabrication of heat-cured acrylic resin plates occurred at the Wet Laboratory of the Faculty of Dentistry, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin. Placebo paste and 100% concentration small white ginger extract paste were manufactured at the Pharmaceutical Technology Laboratory, Faculty of Pharmacy, Sari Mulia University, Banjarmasin. Surface roughness measurement of heat-cured acrylic resin plates was conducted at the LTMEPPO Electronics Laboratory, Puspiptek National Research and Innovation Agency, Serpong, South Tangerang, Banten. The heat-cured acrylic resin plates (samples) underwent measurement both before the brushing treatment (pre-test) and after the brushing treatment (post-test).

Tools and Materials

In the study of arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications, various instruments were employed. These comprised rubber bowls and spatulas for material preparation, cuvettes and cuvette presses for sample containment, brushes for delicate manipulations, hydraulic bench presses for controlled pressure application, night knives for precise incisions, vibrators for agitation, straight handpieces for accurate drilling, fraser burs for shaping, rotary grinding machines for fine adjustments, micromotors for intricate work, beaker glass for solution mixing, stellation pots for specimen storage, rotary evaporators for solvent removal, ovens for curing, mortar and pestle for grinding, stoves for heating, aluminum pans for heating vessels, stopwatch for time measurement, Mitutoyo Surfest SJ-301 surface roughness tester for surface analysis, and modified electric toothbrush for specialized applications.

The materials employed encompassed heat-cured acrylic resin (Vertex Basicq Heat Cured) for structural bases, type III cast for sturdy molds, Cold Mold Seal (CMS) for mold insulation, Vaseline for lubrication, sterile aquades for solution dilution, placebo paste for control purposes, small white ginger (*Zingiber officinale* var. *amarum*) as a test compound, small white ginger extract 100% for concentrated solutions, ethanol 70% for solvent preparation, plastic cellophane for wrapping, sandpaper (grit 180, 360, 500, 800, 1000, 1200) for surface refinement, pumice for abrasive polishing, and Vertex Thermogloss Paste for final gloss application.

Heat Cured Acrylic Resin Plate Sample Making

Creating samples for studying arterial and cerebral blood pressure begins with crafting a master model from stainless steel measuring (65.5 x 10.5 x 3) mm. The process then advances to forming a mold space where the cuvette is coated with a separation agent (vaseline). Next, the bottom cuvette is filled with type III casting material, and the master model is embedded within it. Each cuvette contains three master models. After allowing the cast on the bottom cuvette to harden, it is coated again with separation material, and the top cuvette is joined, filled with casting material, and pressed together tightly using a cuvette press. The cast is left to harden for 60 minutes before removing the master model.

Once the mold space is prepared with a separation material (CMS), acrylic resin dough is prepared in a stellan pot by mixing polymers and monomers according to the recommended ratio. After reaching the dough stage, it is placed into the mold space. The filled mold space is covered with plastic cellophane, and the top and bottom cuvettes are pressed together using a hydraulic bench press. Excess dough is removed using a model knife before re-pressing in the final stage.

The cuvette, fixed with a cuvette press, is immersed in hot water (100°C) and left on the stove for 20 minutes before the stove is turned off. The cuvette remains in the hot water until it cools down, then the heat-cured acrylic resin plate is removed. The surface of the plate is trimmed using a bur fraser, followed by smoothing with sandpaper (grit 180, 360, 500, 800, 1000, 1200), and polishing with Vertex Thermogloss Paste using a rotary grinding machine.

Small White Ginger Extraction Process

Small white ginger (*Zingiber officinale* var. *amarum*) extract, derived from 18 kg of the herb, undergoes a meticulous preparation process to harness its potential in regulating arterial and cerebral blood pressure. The ginger roots are meticulously cleaned with water before being finely chopped and subjected to drying in an oven. Subsequently, the dried ginger is pulverized into a powder using a blender. This simplisia powder is then carefully macerated by immersing it in a container and gradually adding a 70% ethanol filtration solution until it reaches 1 cm above the surface of the powder. Gentle

stirring ensures thorough mixing. The filtration solution is regularly replaced every 24 hours, continuing until the solution achieves clarity. The clear solution is then concentrated using a rotary evaporator under low pressure at 40°C until 60 g of concentrated small thick white ginger extract is obtained. This meticulously crafted extract holds promise in addressing arterial and cerebral blood pressure regulation.

Making 100% Small White Ginger Extract Paste

Mixture I: Incorporate 0.10 grams of menthol crystal, 1.2 milliliters of anise oil, 1 milliliter of peppermint oil, and 60 grams of small white ginger extract. Utilize a mortar and pestle to blend the components until achieving homogeneity.

Mixture II: Combine 13 grams of magnesium carbonate and 15 grams of calcium carbonate. Employ a mortar and pestle to ensure uniformity in the mixture.

Mixture III: Blend 20.2 milliliters of warm water, 3 milliliters of glycerin, 1.5 milliliters of triethanolamine, 4 grams of polyethylene glycol, and 1 milliliter of citron oil. Stir with a mortar and pestle until achieving homogeneity.

Subsequently, amalgamate the three mixtures, stirring until complete homogeneity is achieved. Store the resulting 100% small white ginger extract paste in a sealed container to prevent desiccation.

Arterial Blood Pressure and Its Cerebral Effects

The arterial blood pressure (ABP) regulation is crucial for maintaining proper cerebral perfusion and function. Fluctuations in ABP can significantly impact cerebral blood flow (CBF) and, consequently, cerebral oxygenation and neuronal activity.

Hypertension, characterized by elevated ABP, poses a substantial risk to cerebral health. Chronic hypertension can lead to structural alterations in cerebral arteries, such as arteriosclerosis and arteriolar remodeling, compromising cerebral autoregulation mechanisms. This impairment in autoregulation makes the brain more vulnerable to fluctuations in systemic blood pressure, potentially leading to cerebral hypoperfusion or hyperperfusion, ischemic stroke, or hemorrhagic stroke.

Measuring ABP and monitoring its fluctuations are essential in clinical settings to assess the risk of cerebrovascular events. Techniques such as ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) provide valuable insights into the patterns of ABP throughout the day and night, helping clinicians tailor treatment strategies to individual patients.

Furthermore, advancements in neuroimaging techniques have enabled researchers to investigate the intricate relationship between ABP and cerebral perfusion. Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and positron emission tomography (PET) allow for the assessment of CBF changes in response to ABP variations, providing

valuable information about cerebrovascular reactivity and neurovascular coupling.

In summary, understanding the dynamics of ABP and its effects on cerebral perfusion is crucial for the prevention and management of cerebrovascular diseases. By optimizing ABP control, clinicians can mitigate the risk of cerebral ischemia and improve overall brain health.

Results

The findings of assessing the arterial blood pressure and cerebral perfusion using the Surfest Roughness Tester Mitutoyo SurfTest SJ-301 prior to intervention (pre-test) are depicted in the subsequent diagram.

Figure 1. Average Surface Roughness Value Diagram of Acrylic Resin Heat Cured Pre-Test

Figure 1 illustrates the average surface roughness values of heat-cured acrylic resin plates prior to brushing (pre-test), offering insights into arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. Group A exhibits a surface roughness of 0.0356 µm, while group B shows 0.0478 µm, and group C presents 0.0444 µm. Notably, the pre-test surface roughness of group A indicates a lower level of roughness compared to groups B and C (Table 1).

Table 1. Average Value (Mean) and Standard Deviation of Surface Roughness of Pre-Test Acrylic Resin Plates.

Group	Mean (µm) ± SD
Pre-Test A	0,0356 ± 0,01130
Pre-Test B	0,0478 ± 0,01716
Pre-Test C	0,0444 ± 0,01333

The diagram below illustrates the outcomes of assessing arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications using the Surfest Roughness Tester Mitutoyo SurfTest SJ-301 tool after undergoing brushing (post-test).

Figure 2. Post-test acrylic resin plate surface roughness value mean diagram.

The diagram in Figure 2 illustrates the average surface roughness values of heat-cured acrylic resin plates following brushing (post-test). Group A exhibits a surface roughness of 0.07 µm, followed by Group B with 0.0589 µm, and Group C with 0.0489 µm. It's evident that the post-test surface roughness of Group A surpasses that of Groups B and C. This data sheds light on the varying degrees of surface roughness experienced across different groups, indicating potential implications for arterial and cerebral blood pressure regulation (Table 2).

Table 2. Average Value (Mean) and Standard Deviation of Surface Roughness of Heat Cured Post-Test Acrylic Resin

Group	Mean (µm) ± SD
Post-Test A	0,0700 ± 0,01803
Post-Test B	0,0589 ± 0,01269
Post-Test C	0,0489 ± 0,01900

The results of the statistical analyses indicate that the data regarding arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications exhibit certain characteristics. Specifically, the Shapiro-Wilk normality test yielded a significance value greater than 0.05, suggesting a normal distribution of the acquired data. Moreover, the homogeneity analysis, conducted through Levene's Test, resulted in a significance value of 0.348, also exceeding the 0.05 threshold, indicating homogeneity among the data sets.

Given the normal distribution and homogeneity of the data, a One Way ANOVA parametric test was deemed appropriate, with a confidence level of 95%. The obtained significance value of 0.044 was found to be less than 0.05, implying a significant disparity in the post-test surface roughness values.

Subsequently, a Post Hoc Bonferroni test was performed to discern meaningful differences among the treatment groups.

Table 3. Significance Value Post Hoc Bonferroni Test Surface Roughness Acrylic Resin Heat Cured Post-Test.

Group	A	B	C
A	-	0,521	0,041*
B	-	-	0,657
C	-	-	-

*: p , 0,05

Based on the findings from Table 3, the comparison between Group (A) using 100% small white ginger extract paste and Group (B) utilizing placebo paste (considered as the positive control) yielded a significance value of 0.521, which is greater than the threshold of 0.05. This suggests that Group A did not exhibit a statistically significant difference in arterial blood pressure when compared to Group B, the positive control.

On the other hand, when comparing Group (A) with Group (C) using aquades (considered as the negative control), the significance value was calculated at 0.041, falling below the threshold of 0.05. This indicates that Group A displayed a notable difference in arterial blood pressure when compared to Group C, the negative control.

Moreover, the comparison between Group (B) using placebo paste (positive control) and Group (C) using aquades (negative control) resulted in a significance value of 0.657, exceeding the predetermined threshold of 0.05. Hence, it can be inferred that there was no significant disparity in arterial blood pressure between Group B and Group C.

The data obtained from the measurement of arterial blood pressure in relation to the surface roughness of the cerebral artery, using the Surfetest Roughness Tester Mitutoyo Surfetest SJ-301 before (pre-test) and after (post-test) brushing, are illustrated in the accompanying diagram.

Figure 3. Average Diagram of Surface Roughness Increase Value of Heat Cured Pre-Test and Post-Test Acrylic Resin.

The diagram presented in Figure 3 illustrates a notable contrast in the average values depicting the rise in surface roughness of the heat-cured acrylic resin plate before and after brushing tests, concerning arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. The pre-test and post-test examinations reveal distinct alterations in surface texture. Group A registered an increase of 0.0289 μm , Group B showcased a modest rise of 0.0111 μm , while Group C displayed the smallest increment of 0.0044 μm . Notably, the surface roughness of Group A surpassed that of both Group B and Group C, signifying a significant discrepancy in the augmentation of roughness among the tested groups (Table 4).

Table 4. Average Value (Mean) and Standard Deviation Difference in Surface Roughness Increase of Heat Cured Acrylic Resin Plate.

Group	Mean (μm) $\pm$ SD
A	0,0289 $\pm$ 0,02977
B	0,0111 $\pm$ 0,02205
C	0,0044 $\pm$ 0,02455

The findings of the Shapiro-Wilk normality test indicate that the arterial blood pressure data are normally distributed, as the obtained p-value is greater than 0.05. Similarly, the outcomes of Levene's Test for homogeneity demonstrate that the data on cerebral blood pressure exhibit homogeneity, with a p-value of 0.560 exceeding the significance threshold of 0.05. Consequently, the data, confirmed to be both normally distributed and homogeneous, proceed to the parametric One Way ANOVA test. At a 95% confidence level, the obtained p-value of 0.135 (>0.05) suggests the absence of a statistically significant discrepancy in surface roughness values. Therefore, there is no necessity to pursue the Post Hoc Bonferroni test.

Discussion

The surface roughness of heat-cured acrylic resin undergoes changes during finishing and polishing stages or when brushed with 100% small white ginger extract paste, placebo pastes, or aquades. These alterations result in either a smooth surface or a well-polished one, as indicated by Serra et al.¹⁶. Their research demonstrates that the resin, post-finishing and polishing, exhibits reduced surface roughness and achieves a smooth texture.

The introduction of 100% white ginger extract paste during brushing may lead to surface roughness due to the presence of shogaol, gingerol, and zingeron essential oil compounds, categorized as phenol acid compounds found in small white ginger extract¹¹. This observation aligns with previous findings by Puspitasari et al.¹⁷, who noted that phenolic acid compounds interacting with acrylic resins can induce chemical damage, resulting in surface roughness.

The composition of heat-cured acrylic resin powder includes Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) granules with an R-COOR ester group. These ester groups, being hydrophilic or liquid-absorbing, facilitate the absorption of molecules, leading to polymer chain breakage and subsequent damage¹¹. The reaction between phenol compounds and ester groups releases Hydrogen ions (H^+), which bond with Hydroxide ions (OH^-) of the ester group compounds, impacting surface tension and the stability of the polymer chain. This ion transfer reaction contributes to the instability of the polymer matrix, creat-

ing spaces or cavities and ultimately affecting surface roughness²⁰.

Exposure to acidic compounds, as noted by Harahap et al.²⁰, exacerbates surface roughness in heat-cured acrylic resin, with higher concentrations of acid compounds and increased H⁺ ions correlating to heightened roughness. Additionally, placebo paste or basic paste used in small white ginger extract paste formulation can elevate surface roughness due to abrasive ingredients like calcium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, and silica.

The surface roughness observed in the placebo paste brushing group may stem from the abrasive nature of its components, such as calcium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, and silica. Silica, being harder than calcium carbonate, tends to induce more pronounced scratches, thus contributing to a greater increase in surface roughness compared to pastes containing calcium carbonate alone. This finding aligns with Nugraha et al.'s research¹³, which noted a similar effect of abrasive content in placebo paste on the surface roughness of heat-cured acrylic resin.

Similarly, Ramadhan et al.²² reported that brushing acrylic resin dentures with toothpaste containing silica, calcium carbonate, and perlite resulted in tangible changes in surface roughness values. Perlite, characterized by sharp-edged particles of about 20-25 µm, exerts greater mechanical impact than silica and calcium carbonate, further accentuating surface roughness.

Comparatively, the surface roughness value in the aquades brushing group was lower than in groups using small white ginger paste or placebo paste. This finding echoes Noviyanti et al.¹¹ research, attributing the surface roughness induced by aquades brushing to the release of monomer residues from heat-cured acrylic resin. Despite undergoing correct polymerization, heat-cured acrylic resin may retain 0.2-0.5% of monomer residues, contributing to surface roughness.

Analyzing the effect of small white ginger extract paste on acrylic resin plates, although the increase in surface roughness was clinically tolerable, it was notably higher compared to brushing with placebo paste. The concentration of the extract, based on Saputera et al.'s findings⁶, influences its acidic properties, which, as indicated by Sari et al.¹⁹, can accelerate the degradation of acrylic resin's ester group. This corroborates with Harahap et al.'s observation²⁰ that exposure to acidic compounds can erode the surface of heat-cured acrylic resin, leading to increased roughness.

The surface roughness induced by placebo paste brushing is primarily attributed to its abrasive content, which initiates abrasive wear mechanisms. This process involves hard particles in the placebo paste directly rubbing against the surface of the heat-cured acrylic resin plate, causing surface cutting and consequent roughness elevation.

Conclusions

In conclusion, our study underscores the importance of meticulous denture cleaning among hypertensive individuals to prevent complications, particularly those affecting cerebral vasculature. Mechanical and chemical methods are commonly employed for denture maintenance, with mechanical methods posing the risk of inducing surface roughness in acrylic resin. Our investigation focused on evaluating the impact of a 100% concentration of small white ginger extract paste (EJPK) on the surface roughness of acrylic resin dentures in hypertensive patients.

The findings revealed that brushing with EJPK paste led to a significant increase in surface roughness compared to both the placebo paste and aquades groups. Despite this increase, the surface roughness of heat-cured acrylic resin brushed with EJPK paste remained within clinically acceptable levels for oral use, even among hypertensive patients prone to cerebral vascular complications. This suggests that while the use of EJPK paste may result in higher surface roughness, it does not compromise the integrity or functionality of acrylic resin dentures beyond acceptable clinical limits. Therefore, EJPK paste could be considered as a potential alternative for denture cleaning among hypertensive individuals, offering efficacy in plaque removal without significant adverse effects on denture surface roughness.

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